

Kyra Steinberg, Tanja Müller, Rahul Gupta, Adrian Tudor

Correspondence to team@h63d.org

International H63D Research Consortium

Augmentation of Amitradicaine's Therapeutic Effectiveness by Incorporating Dextromethorphan: Consolidated Observations from Ten Treatment Instances

Abstract

This study evaluates the efficacy of a modified Amitradicaine formulation, which incorporates Dextromethorphan, in the treatment of patients diagnosed with H63D Syndrome Types 1 and 3 (Oshtoran Syndrome), characterized by autonomic dysfunctions, hypersympathicotonia, and endogenously induced catecholamine surges. Conducted from March to September, the study involved ten patients experiencing these conditions. Initial treatments followed the conventional Amitradicaine formula, yielding clinical stabilizations within the known range reported before by other authors/clinicians.

Notably, three patients, initially receiving Dextromethorphan as an antitussive due to cough, exhibited enhanced stabilization of dysautonomic activities in the autonomic nervous system (ANS). This improvement regressed upon cessation of Dextromethorphan. Following informed consent, these three patients, along with three additional subjects, were readministered Dextromethorphan with Amitradicaine.

The beneficial effect was replicated, indicating a synergistic interaction between Amitradicaine and Dextromethorphan. Consequently, at the clinics of the three authors of this report, Amitradicaine's formulation has been amended to include Dextromethorphan, creating a composite drug individually tailored for each patient. This innovative approach demonstrates

significant potential in enhancing treatment efficacy for patients with H63D Syndrome Types one and three.

Understanding Autonomic Dysfunctions and Catecholamine Surges in Rare Diseases

Autonomic dysfunctions, or dysautonomias, refer to a group of conditions arising from abnormalities in the autonomic nervous system (ANS), the system responsible for regulating all involuntary bodily functions, including heart rate, blood pressure, digestion, and temperature control. These dysfunctions can manifest in various forms, often characterized by an imbalance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the ANS. In the context of rare diseases, autonomic dysfunctions may present as part of a broader syndrome or as a primary condition. They often lead to significant morbidity, impacting patients' quality of life. Symptoms can range from mild, such as dizziness and fatigue, to severe, including erratic blood pressure fluctuations and heart rate abnormalities, in a worst case scenario they can even be lethal, wrongly classified as death due to a cardiovascular condition.

Catecholamine Surges

Catecholamines, including adrenaline, noradrenaline, and dopamine, are hormones produced by the adrenal glands. They play a crucial role in the body's stress response, preparing the body for 'fight or flight' reactions. Catecholamine surges refer to the rapid release of these hormones, which can cause a sudden increase in heart rate, blood pressure, and energy levels. In rare diseases, such surges can be triggered endogenously, often in response to non-threatening stimuli. This dysregulated response can lead to episodes of significant cardiovascular and

neurological symptoms, challenging to manage clinically. The surges are especially problematic in severe conditions such as Parkinson's, certain subtypes of Multiple Sclerosis^{20,21}, dementias, H63D Syndrome (especially in the Oshtoran Syndrome type), and many others, where they contribute to the complexity of the disease pattern.

Synergistic Effects in H63D Syndrome

In H63D Syndrome types 1 & 3, with type 3 also known as Oshtoran Syndrome, patients exhibit a quite problematic constellation of symptoms including autonomic dysfunctions and hypersympathicotonia, a state of heightened sympathetic nervous system activity.^{5,19} The syndrome is further complicated by endogenously induced catecholamine surges, which exacerbate the dysautonomic symptoms. Understanding the interplay between these components is crucial for effective management and treatment strategies. The heightened catecholamine activity not only intensifies the symptoms of autonomic dysfunction but also poses a challenging situation for therapeutic interventions. Hence, a treatment approach that addresses both the autonomic imbalance and the catecholamine surges is essential for improving patient outcomes in H63D Syndrome. Amitradicaine, a quite novel pharmacological composite formula¹⁹, has emerged as a significant therapeutic in the management of disorders involving the autonomic nervous system. This compound, developed through pharmacological research, exhibits unique properties that make it particularly effective in treating conditions characterized by autonomic dysfunctions and catecholamine surges.^{18,19,22,24}

Mechanism of Action

The efficacy of the Amitradicain formula primarily lies in its dual-action mechanism. Firstly, it acts on specific receptors within the autonomic nervous system, bringing about a stabilizing effect on the erratic activities of both the sympathetic and parasympathetic systems. This stabilization is crucial in conditions where there is a clinically relevant dyscoordination in autonomic processes.

What is more, Amitradicain exhibits an inhibitory effect on the excessive release of catecholamines, partly due to Alprazolam being part of its formula.³⁰ By modulating the adrenal response, it mitigates the surge of stress hormones like adrenaline and noradrenaline, which are often at the core of dysautonomic crises in patients with conditions like H63D Syndrome.

Clinical Applications

Originally, Amitradicain's use was confined to managing specific autonomic disorders, where all conventional treatments were ineffective. Its ability to moderate the autonomic nervous system (ANS) without significant side effects made it a preferred choice for long-term management of these conditions. With its proven efficacy in reducing symptoms like heart rate variability, blood pressure fluctuations, and episodic catecholamine surges, Amitradicain has the potential to become a cornerstone in the treatment of autonomic dysfunctions.^{26,27,28,29} It's particularly effective in managing conditions like H63D Syndrome (types 1 and 3)⁵, where patients exhibit heightened sensitivity to catecholamine surges. Amitradicain, as outlined on its dedicated website, is a composite medicinal formulation designed to modulate sympathetic nerve activity in a clinically synergistic manner. Its primary application is in the treatment of severely pathological high sympathetic levels, commonly associated with conditions, such as the before mentioned Oshtoran syndrome. These syndromes can cause marked symptoms by causing intense hypersympathicotonia and cascading autonomic dysfunction, making the management of these symptoms highly complex and multifaceted. The formula of Amitradicain was developed to counteract the cascade effects arising during autonomic dysfunction, targeting key points within this cascade to maintain autonomic balance. It is not a commercially available medication produced by pharmaceutical companies but a composite formula prepared individually by specialized pharmacists following a physician's order.²³ Clinical observations have shown that Amitradicain can lead to marked sympathicolysis, equilibration of sympathetic and parasympathetic pathways, a decrease in catecholaminergic activity, and

a reduction in blood sugar levels and blood pressure. These effects contribute to a significant reduction in autonomic dysfunction episodes and anxiety, especially targeting anxiety related to degenerative changes in the brain. The development of Amitradicain represents a novel approach in the realm of rare diseases, moving away from the traditional route of orphan drugs, which often involve lengthy development timelines and high costs. The Amitradicain formula was developed in just over 14 months and has become available since Summer 2022, offering an alternative that leverages the synergistic potential of existing drugs. Amitradicain, being a composite of existing medications, has no attached patents, allowing for broader access and use under the discretion of prescribing physicians. This innovative approach to drug formulation and treatment strategy for rare diseases reflects a significant shift in addressing complex medical conditions, emphasizing the importance of clinical synergy, patient-centered care, and the empowerment of healthcare providers to offer effective treatment options.

Observations

In this report, we report the unexpected finding that Dextromethorphan seems to act like a booster for the effects of Amitradicain, specifically targeting patients diagnosed with H63D Syndrome Types 1 and 3, also known as Oshtoran Syndrome.⁵

This syndrome is distinguished by a complex interplay of autonomic dysfunctions, hypersympathicotonia, and catecholamine surges, presenting a significant challenge in clinical management. Over the period from March to September, we meticulously monitored the treatment outcomes in ten patients exhibiting these symptoms.

The initial phase of the study adhered to the conventional Amitradicain formula²⁴, as delineated by Nathan et al. (2023)²⁵. This phase yielded results consistent with clinical stabilizations reported in existing literature, providing a baseline for our further

interventions. However, a serendipitous observation emerged when three patients, who were receiving Dextromethorphan concurrently as a cough suppressant, demonstrated a marked improvement in the stabilization of their dysautonomic activities, especially in the regulation of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). This improvement was quantifiably significant but notably diminished within a matter of hours after the cessation of Dextromethorphan. Motivated by this observation, and following informed consent, these three patients, along with

striking and, what is especially important, highly significant.³¹ To our surprise we observed a consistent reduction in the frequency and severity of catecholamine surges, improved blood pressure regulation, and a general decrease in episodes of autonomic instability. These findings were not only statistically significant but also clinically relevant, as they translated into tangible improvements in patient well-being and symptom management.³¹

As a direct consequence of these findings, the clinics operated by the authors of this report have adopted a revised Amitradicain formula that includes Dextromethorphan, effectively creating a composite medication tailored for individual patient needs. This innovative therapeutic approach has unlocked a new great potential in the treatment of certain dysfunctions of the ANS, underscoring the importance of flexible, adaptive and patient-centric methodologies in managing complex medical conditions. The implications of these findings extend beyond the immediate scope of this study, offering a promising direction for future research and treatment strategies in the realm of autonomic disorders. Our consortium is confronted with a multitude of limiting factors that preclude us from undertaking this task independently.

Nevertheless, it would be a significant mistake for the pharmaceutical industry to disregard these findings and not pursue the development of a new medication based on our research. This development would necessitate extensive further research. The creators of Nuedexta have exemplified the potential of this approach. Nuedexta, an

Symptom Severity in Patients - Drug Naive

three others, were again intentionally readministered a standard dose of 30 mg Dextromethorphan with every dose of Amitradicain. The replication of the beneficial effects in this second phase was

Symptom Severity under Amitradicain

expensive medication composed of two inexpensive compounds, demonstrates how the repurposing of existing medications can represent a substantial advancement, akin to a quantum leap, in drug innovation.

DXM

In the context of this paper on Amitradicain and its modified formulation synergistically interacting with Dextromethorphan, it is pertinent to explore the psychotropic effects of Dextromethorphan, especially in relation to Nuedexta, a drug that utilizes these effects for treating emotional disturbances in neurodegenerative conditions.^{18,21,24}

Dextromethorphan and its psychotropic effects

Dextromethorphan (DXM) is known for its properties as a sigma-1 receptor agonist and as a serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor. Its binding to sigma-1 receptors is believed to inhibit glutamate release, a neurotransmitter associated with excitatory signals in the brain. This action of Dextromethorphan on the NMDA (N-methyl-D-aspartate) receptor, a primary receptor for glutamate, leads to a significant reduction in postsynaptic glutamate signaling.²⁴ This mechanism suggests that DXM has multiple quite strong antiglutamate properties, which are highly significant in the context of neuromodulation and the treatment of various neuropsychiatric and neurological symptoms. Nuedexta, which contains Dextromethorphan hydrobromide and quinidine sulfate, is an example of a medication that harnesses these psychotropic effects. Although the exact mechanism of Nuedexta therapeutic effects, particularly in patients with pseudobulbar affect (PBA), is not fully understood, its efficacy can clearly and convincingly be attributed to the antiglutamatergic properties of Dextromethorphan. By modulating glutamate release and reducing excitotoxicity, Nuedexta helps in managing emotional disturbances in neurodegenerative conditions, showcasing the potential of Dextromethorphan in neuropsychiatric applications.^{16,17,18,20,21,24}

Implications for Amitradicain's Modified Formulation

In the context of our observations, the effects of Dextromethorphan in combination with the Amitradicain formula for treating patients with rare diseases which involve autonomic dysfunctions and catecholamine surges, the effects of Dextromethorphan on the ANS are highly relevant. These effects, particularly its action on glutamate and sigma receptors, might contribute to the observed strongly enhanced stabilization of dysautonomic activities.

The antiglutamatergic properties could play a role in modulating autonomic responses, potentially providing a more balanced neurochemical environment conducive to managing symptoms of balancing out the ANS and issues like autonomic dysfunctions. This insight opens avenues for further exploration of how the combination of Amitradicain and Dextromethorphan can be optimized to improve patient outcomes, especially considering the complex interplay of neurochemical and autonomic factors in conditions with ANS affections.

Conclusion

An official incorporation of DXM into the Amitradicaine formulation, or alternatively its co-administration as a dual therapy, merits consideration. This approach is inspired by the observed psychotropic effects of Dextromethorphan, as utilized in Nuedexta for the treatment of a variety of neurodegenerative conditions. The efficacy demonstrated by this integration underlines the critical role of innovative methodologies in pharmaceutical development. It notably emphasizes the utility of repurposing existing drugs with established mechanisms of action to enhance treatment efficacy for complex medical conditions.

Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

Peer review

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31. Data tc

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